

1 **Diabetes as a compounding factor in COVID-19-mediated male subfertility**

2

3 Qingkui Jiang¹, Thomas Linn², Karl Drlica³, Lanbo Shi^{1*}

4

5 ¹Public Health Research Institute, New Jersey Medical School, Rutgers Biomedical and Health
6 Sciences, Rutgers The State University of New Jersey, Newark, New Jersey, USA

7 ²Clinical Research Unit, Centre of Internal Medicine, Justus-Liebig-University (JLU), Giessen,
8 Germany

9 ³Public Health Research Institute and Department of Microbiology, Biochemistry, and Molecular
10 Genetics, New Jersey Medical School, Rutgers Biomedical and Health Sciences, Rutgers The State
11 University of New Jersey, Newark, New Jersey, USA

12 *shila@njms.rutgers.edu

13

14 **Key words:** SARS-CoV-2; inflammation; diabetes; spermatogenesis; male reproductive hormones;
15 male subfertility

16 **Abstract (176 words)**

17 Recent work indicates that male fertility is compromised by SARS-CoV-2 infection. Direct effects
18 derive from the presence of viral entry receptors (ACE and/or CD147) on the surface of testicular
19 cells, such as spermatocytes, Sertoli cells, and Leydig cells. Indirect effects on testis and
20 concentrations of male reproductive hormones derive from 1) virus-stimulated inflammation; 2)
21 viral-induced diabetes, and 3) an interaction between diabetes and inflammation that exacerbates
22 the deleterious effect of each perturbation. Reproductive hormones affected include testosterone,
23 luteinizing hormone, and follicle-stimulating hormone. Reduction of male fertility is also observed
24 with other viral infections, but the global pandemic of COVID-19 makes demographic and public
25 health implications of reduced male fertility of major concern, especially if it occurs in the absence
26 of serious symptoms that would otherwise encourage vaccination. Clinical documentation of
27 COVID-19-associated male subfertility is now warranted to obtain quantitative relationships
28 between infection severity and subfertility; mechanistic studies using animal models may reveal
29 ways to mitigate the problem. In the meantime, the possibility of subfertility due to COVID-19
30 should enter considerations of vaccine hesitancy by reproductive-age males.

31

32 **Introduction (3400 words)**

33 Although most persons infected with SARS-CoV-2 experience only mild-to-moderate respiratory
34 illness and recover without special treatment, some progress to severe disease that is often
35 associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome¹. Thus, COVID-19 was initially considered to
36 be a lung disease². Subsequent experimental and clinical studies now indicate that SARS-CoV-2
37 infection damages multiple organs, including brain³, kidney⁴, pancreas⁵, and testis⁶. Moreover,
38 some infected individuals suffer from long-term sequelae, such as extreme fatigue, muscle
39 weakness, low-grade fever, new onset of diabetes, and hypertension^{7,8}. Therefore, COVID-19
40 cannot be treated as a common viral infection that appears to come and go.

41 Key features of the male reproductive system make it vulnerable to damage by COVID-19. For
42 example, spermatogonia, Sertoli cells, and Leydig cells reside outside the blood-testis barrier and
43 are therefore susceptible to viral infection. Direct SARS-CoV-2 infection of cells associated with
44 sperm development and effects of inflammation are both likely to compromise male reproductive
45 potential⁹. Moreover, synthesis and secretion of male reproductive hormones, such as
46 gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing
47 hormone (LH), and testosterone are sensitive to various types of inflammation¹⁰. These
48 observations, plus several other lines of evidence, indicate a negative impact of SARS-CoV-2
49 infection on male fertility, at least during serious disease^{6,11}.

50 The mechanisms underlying testicular dysfunction in male COVID-19 patients remain poorly
51 understood. In addition to effects from direct infection and inflammation, an under-appreciated
52 factor is diabetes. This well-documented risk factor for male subfertility¹² may contribute
53 significantly to low fertility in COVID-19. Indeed, diabetes often occurs in COVID-19-patients
54 with pre-diabetes and with patients lacking prior glucose metabolism disorders¹³. Below we

55 describe viremia-induced male subfertility, followed by a discussion of potential mechanisms by
56 which SARS-CoV-2 infection causes male hypogonadism. We argue that diabetes aggravates the
57 negative impact of SARS-CoV-2 infection on male reproductive potential.

58 **Viremia and male subfertility**

59 **Lessons from other viral infections**

60 Viral infections have long been associated with male subfertility. In a recent example, men infected
61 with Zika virus exhibited decreased semen quality and the presence of viral RNA in spermatozoa¹⁴.
62 Findings from murine infection models associate reduced semen quality with persistence of Zika
63 virus and induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines/chemokines in testicular cells (Sertoli, Leydig,
64 and epididymal epithelial cells)^{15,16}. In another example, 15 to 30% of adult males infected with
65 mumps virus develop epididymo-orchitis and subfertility¹⁷; murine studies indicate that the
66 underlying mechanism is related to increased innate immune response in Sertoli, Leydig, and germ
67 cells. Similarly, infection of human spermatozoa by immunodeficiency virus (HIV) compromises
68 male fertility^{18,19}, as demonstrated by detectable virus in seminal fluids, severe testicular atrophy,
69 and chronic orchitis with progressive hypogonadism²⁰⁻²². In a fourth example, patients with
70 chronic infection by hepatitis virus C exhibit a decrease in semen volume, sperm count, sperm
71 motility, and testosterone²³. Finally, a meta-analysis of the human papillomavirus in semen reveals
72 a positive correlation between virus positivity and an elevated risk of male infertility²⁴. Thus, a
73 precedence exists for viral infection-induced male subfertility: SARS-CoV-2 infection is simply
74 another example.

75 **SARS-CoV-2 in testes**

76 It is well known that SARS-CoV-2 infects host cells through an interaction of its spike protein
77 with the host ACE2 receptor, which is expressed on the surface of several cell types²⁵. High-level
78 expression of ACE2 in human testes²⁶, mainly in spermatogonia, Leydig cells, and Sertoli cells²⁷,
79 suggests testis susceptibility to circulating virus. In addition, CD147, which mediates host-cell
80 entry for viruses such as HIV²⁸ and SARS-CoV²⁹, also functions as a receptor for SARS-CoV-2³⁰.
81 This observation has important implications, given that CD147 is expressed in Sertoli cells, Leydig
82 cells, and germ cells of all stages, and that it is also a critical regulator in spermatogenesis³¹. Thus,
83 SARS-CoV-2 may impact testicular function by specific binding to the two different receptors
84 **(Fig. 1)**.

85 Patient data are consistent with direct effects of SARS-CoV-2 on male fertility. Two studies
86 of severe disease detected SARS-CoV-2 particles in testis cells. In one, two out of five postmortem
87 testis biopsies revealed virus⁶; in the other, one out of five were virus-positive postmortem, and
88 one live biopsy was virus-positive³². Clinical manifestations of testicular injury in COVID-19
89 include orchitis³³, structural change of testis³⁴, spermatogenesis impairment^{6,35}, and significant
90 changes of major male reproductive hormones, such as increased serum levels of LH and FSH and
91 decreased testosterone^{36,37}. Since testicular damage is often found without direct evidence of virus
92 in the testis, other factors likely contribute indirectly to testicular dysfunction. Below we discuss
93 two indirect COVID-19-associated factors, inflammation and diabetes; we postulate that their
94 interaction exacerbates male reproductive damage.

95

96

97

98

99 **Figure. 1. Direct infection of testicular cells by SARS-CoV-2.** By binding to the highly
 100 expressed viral entry receptors on testicular cells, specifically the Sertoli cells, Leydig cells, and
 101 spermatogonia, SARS-CoV-2 may infect these cells and cause direct cell damage, metabolic
 102 reprogramming, and/or immune responses. The result would be cell dysfunction and apoptosis.

103

104 **Viral infection-induced inflammation**

105 Inflammation in the reproductive tract is associated with male subfertility. For example,
 106 asymptomatic focal inflammatory lesions are found in approximately half of testicular biopsies
 107 from males exhibiting impaired fertility³⁸, and levels of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1β, IL-6
 108 and TNF) are elevated in seminal plasma of infertile males³⁹. Mechanisms of inflammation on
 109 testicular dysfunction have been revealed by *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. Inflammatory molecules,
 110 either produced locally or derived from systemic inflammation, damage germ cells and somatic

111 cells by activating the Janus kinase-signal transducer and activator of transcription pathway and
112 the MAPK pathway^{40,41}. Our recent work also shows that testicular inflammation is associated
113 with impaired spermatogenesis and Leydig cell dysfunction and apoptosis⁴². Inflammation also
114 acts by dysregulating hormone secretion. For example, in the mouse hypothalamic GnRH neuronal
115 cell line, neuroinflammation-induced cytokines, specifically the leukemia inhibitory factor, repress
116 GnRH gene expression by activating the MAPK pathway⁴³. Proinflammatory cytokines, such as
117 IL-1, TNF and IL-6, also negatively affect pituitary function, reducing the synthesis and/or
118 secretion of FSH and LH⁴⁴. Thus, inflammation appears to contribute to male subfertility at
119 multiple levels.

120 COVID-19 is an inflammatory disease, as defined by systemic production and secretion of
121 proinflammatory cytokines/chemokines⁴⁵. Since infection and inflammation are important triggers
122 of male infertility in general⁴⁶, inflammation can be a good candidate for poor male reproductive
123 outcome associated with COVID-19 (**Fig. 2A**). Indeed, seminiferous tubular injury and reduced
124 numbers of Leydig cells associated with mild inflammation are seen in the testis of COVID-19
125 patients⁴⁷. Moreover, clinical data from COVID-19 patients indicate that reduction of serum
126 testosterone is negatively associated with levels of C-reactive protein (a marker of inflammation)
127 and predictive of poor prognosis for COVID-19 patients^{36,48}. Little else is known about the
128 mechanisms underlying inflammation effects on male reproductive outcome in COVID-19.

129

130 **Figure. 2: Indirect effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on male fertility.** Three interconnected
 131 pathways during COVID-19 negatively impact male fertility. Inflammation (A) and diabetes (B)
 132 each serve as a secondary factor of SARS-CoV-2 infection to independently affect the
 133 hypothalamic-pituitary-testis (HPT) axis and/or testicular cells by direct impact or through other
 134 mediators. C: The interaction between inflammation and diabetes exacerbates the deleterious
 135 effect of each individual perturbation, leading to male subfertility.

136

137 Although inflammation recedes in COVID-19 patients when they recover from primary disease,
 138 new evidence indicates that the effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on male fertility are long-lasting.
 139 For example, about a month after recovering from COVID-19, four out of five patients admitted
 140 to the intensive care unit, three out of 26 hospitalized, and one among 12 non-hospitalized showed
 141 azoospermia⁴⁹. A case study also described a male of reproductive age who exhibited reduced
 142 sperm concentration and sperm count, increased abnormal sperm morphology, and reduced sperm

143 vitality four months after recovery from COVID-19⁵⁰. Thus, factors other than the initial
144 inflammation during COVID-19 persist that negatively affect male fertility. Below we consider
145 diabetes as a persisting factor in the reduction of male fertility because hyperglycemia is frequently
146 seen in COVID-19 patients (46% during hospitalization, 36% of which continue to show
147 hyperglycemia in the following six months)⁵¹ and because diabetes is a major risk factor for male
148 subfertility.

149 **COVID-19-associated diabetes reduces male fertility**

150 **Lessons from other viral infections**

151 Infection with a variety of viruses is often associated with the onset of diabetes. For example,
152 cytomegalovirus infection contributes to the pathogenesis of both type-1 and type-2 diabetes^{52,53}.
153 Indeed, persons with a history of cytomegalovirus infection exhibit a 12-fold greater chance for
154 developing type-2 diabetes⁵⁴. Diabetes is also highly prevalent in hepatitis C virus-infected
155 individuals (50% of adult cirrhotic patients infected with the virus develop diabetes mellitus
156 compared to 9% of patients with cirrhosis in the absence of hepatitis C infection⁵⁵). In an example
157 similar to SARS-COV-2 infection, about 50% of SARS-CoV-infected patients lacking a history
158 of diabetes developed high blood glucose levels within two weeks of hospitalization. Thus, SARS-
159 CoV infection can markedly influence glucose homeostasis, at least in the acute phase of disease⁵⁶.
160 The onset of diabetes during SARS-CoV-2 infection may be common rather than exceptional; if
161 so, diabetes is expected to be a significant contributor to male subfertility.

162 **Reciprocal relationship between COVID-19 and diabetes**

163 In a case-series study of 5,700 patients hospitalized with COVID-19 in the New York City area,
164 34% were diabetic⁵⁷. Diabetes was associated with disease progression to severe COVID-19 (odds

165 ratio of 3.07)⁵⁸ and with a 3.2-fold increase in COVID-19-related mortality⁵⁹. Insulin resistance
166 marker (triglyceride and glucose index) was also found to associate with the severity and mortality
167 of COVID-19⁶⁰. Uncontrolled blood glucose levels may contribute to the development of severe
168 disease in diabetic COVID-19 patients by promoting virus replication and cytokine production in
169 monocytes⁶¹. High glucose levels also result in an exacerbated pro-inflammatory response and
170 acute metabolic decompensation of pre-existing diabetes⁶². These observations clearly show that
171 diabetes is a risk factor for worse prognosis in COVID-19.

172 A reciprocal relationship also appears to exist. SARS-CoV-2 infection is reported to lead to
173 the onset of insulin resistance and acute hyperglycemia in people without diabetes and to the
174 development of diabetes in patients with pre-diabetes⁶³⁻⁶⁵. Two underlying mechanisms are likely
175 involved. First, infection of pancreatic cells by SARS-CoV-2 can lead to the onset of
176 hyperglycemia and/or diabetes. Indeed, ACE2 mRNA is expressed in both the islets and exocrine
177 glands of the pancreas at a level about 1.6 times higher than seen in the lung⁶⁶. Moreover, viral
178 infiltration of pancreatic islets⁶⁷ and pancreatic injury⁶⁶ are seen with COVID-19 patients; such
179 infiltration might contribute to an acute β -cell dysfunction, leading to acute hyperglycemia⁵⁶.
180 Second, proinflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species (ROS), produced during SARS-
181 CoV-2 infection, are known to induce insulin resistance⁶⁸. In the case of circulating inflammatory
182 markers in obesity, such as TNF, activation of IKK β /NF κ B pathway is associated with induction
183 of insulin resistance and type-2 diabetes in mice⁶⁹. In addition, elevated ROS levels trigger insulin
184 resistance in cell culture and mouse models⁷⁰. Thus, poor glycemic control and a cytokine storm
185 during SARS-CoV-2 infection can act as a vicious cycle, reciprocally leading to severe symptoms
186 and poor prognosis of COVID-19 patients with diabetes^{71,72}. An international collaboration, the
187 CoviDIAB Project (covidiab.e-dendrite.com), seeks to understand the pathogenesis, management,

188 and outcomes of COVID-19-related diabetes⁷³. To this effort we add male subfertility as another
189 potentially serious consequence of COVID-19-associated poor glycaemic control (**Fig. 2B**), as
190 discussed below.

191 **Diabetes during COVID-19 affects male fertility**

192 We and others have shown that diabetes is associated with testicular damage in murine
193 models^{42,74,75}. As expected, treatments that lower hyperglycemia can restore spermatogenesis and
194 steroidogenesis in diabetic animals (increased sperm count, sperm motility, and testosterone)^{74,76,77}.
195 In addition, administration of metformin, the first-line treatment for type-2 diabetes in men with
196 diabetic complications, improves sperm concentration and sperm chromatin integrity⁷⁸.

197 Mechanistic studies using animal models show that diabetes disrupts the function of glucose
198 transporters in spermatozoa and Leydig cells⁷⁹. Hyperglycemia damages testes by activating two
199 major pathways, the diacylglycerol-protein kinase C pathway and the polyol pathway⁸⁰. Overall,
200 these findings indicate that the onset of hyperglycemia, even in the absence of obvious testicular
201 viral infection or inflammation, can lead to poor reproductive outcomes in COVID-19 patients
202 (**Fig. 2B**)^{71,72}.

203 **Inflammation-diabetes interaction**

204 Diabetes, particularly type-2 diabetes, is widely accepted as an inflammatory disease⁸¹. In diabetes,
205 hyperglycemia and inflammation appear to stimulate each other. On one hand, hyperglycemia
206 often correlates with elevated systemic inflammation. For example, an acute increase in plasma
207 IL-6, TNF, and IL-18 is observed in humans after receiving intravenous glucose; the increase is
208 more pronounced in subjects having impaired glucose tolerance⁸². Moreover, hyperglycemia
209 drives IL-1 β production in obesity through activation of the thioredoxin-interacting protein⁸³. On
210 the other hand, inflammation has long been recognized as a critical player in the onset and/or

211 progression of diabetes⁸⁴. It is known that TNF-signaling cascades activate the c-Jun amino-
212 terminal kinase, leading to phosphorylation of serine 307 in insulin receptor substrate-1. This event
213 causes insulin unresponsiveness⁸⁵. Additionally, IL-1 β affects β -cells through a direct cytotoxic
214 effect⁸⁶ and/or by driving tissue inflammation within islet cells⁸⁷, thereby impairing β -cell function
215 and insulin sensitivity. IL-6 also impairs insulin metabolism by increasing the expression and
216 activity of the insulin-degrading enzyme⁸⁸. Finally, pro-inflammatory cytokine-related ROS
217 overproduction, associated with high neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio during SARS-CoV-2
218 infection⁶⁸, can trigger insulin resistance that is observed both *in vitro* and *in vivo*⁷⁰. Collectively,
219 the interaction of diabetes and inflammation likely increases complications with a variety of
220 diseases, one of which is male subfertility.

221 **Inflammation-diabetes interaction worsens male subfertility during COVID-19**

222 We recently found that hyperglycemia interacts with inflammation to cause hypogonadism in
223 diabetic and pre-diabetic mice⁴², thereby linking diabetes, inflammation, and male subfertility. In
224 this work, we used homozygous, leptin-resistant diabetic *db/db* mice that are characterized by
225 hypogonadism, hyperglycemia, and testicular inflammation with increased IL-1 β and chemokine
226 (C-C motif) ligand 2 (CCL2). The latter is a key member of the cytokine storm associated with
227 COVID-19 severity⁸⁹. Chemical inhibition of CCL2 protects murine and human Leydig cells from
228 malfunction and apoptosis, it reverses the diabetic condition, and it ameliorates hypogonadism in
229 the *db/db* mice^{42,90}. Moreover, in a diabetes model induced by a high-fat diet, *Ccl2*-deficient mice
230 are protected from development of diabetes and testicular dysfunction⁴².

231 Overall, findings from Leydig cell work and mouse studies fit with clinical studies in which a
232 reduction of serum levels of CCL2 is associated with improvement of diabetic conditions and
233 recovery from hypogonadism in a cohort of infertile men having a history of metabolic syndrome⁴².

234 Although we did not address the direct impact of diabetes on subfertility in our murine and clinical
235 studies, the observation that hypogonadism reverses with improved glucose control and reduced
236 inflammation argues for a functional role of diabetes in dysregulation of male reproduction.

237 We propose that deterioration of glycemic control associated with SARS-COV-2 infection has
238 a greater negative impact on male fertility in patients with diabetes or prediabetes. Male COVID-
239 19 patients experiencing both a cytokine storm and diabetes could exhibit severely harmed
240 reproductive potential through compounding effects of two aggravating factors on testicular cells.
241 The result is impaired spermatogenesis, Sertoli and Leydig cell dysfunction and loss, and a
242 dysregulated immune environment in testes^{42,75,80}. Although COVID-19-associated inflammation
243 is transient, diabetes can be a long-lasting complication, emphasizing the long-term threat of
244 COVID-19 to male fertility (**Fig. 2C**).

245 **Inflammation and diabetes share factors contributing to male subfertility**

246 **Reactive oxygen species.** Although low levels of ROS are needed as signaling molecules,
247 overproduction of ROS under inflammatory and/or diabetic conditions often leads to oxidative
248 stress expected to damage cell functions. Several studies indicate that inflammation is
249 accompanied by ROS stress. One reports that treatment with cytokines (TNF, IL-1 β , and IFN- γ)
250 increases ROS in human retinal pigment epithelial cells⁹¹. In another, glomerular cells treated with
251 TNF and IL-6 show ROS-mediated stress and damaged glomerular permeability⁹². Similar to
252 inflammation, diabetes is also associated with increased ROS stress. Hyperglycemia in diabetic
253 patients elevate ROS production through mitochondrial respiratory chain enzymes, peroxidases,
254 lipoxygenases, nitric oxide synthases, cyclooxygenases, and xanthine oxidases⁹³. Increased ROS
255 level has also been observed in pancreatic islets of diabetic mice⁹⁴. Collectively these findings
256 suggest an important role for ROS in inflammation and diabetes-related complications.

257 In terms of male fertility, low levels of ROS are necessary for sperm capacitation and
258 hyperactivation, but elevated levels of ROS likely contribute to male subfertility. For example,
259 presumptive ROS-mediated sperm defects, such as poor sperm membrane integrity and high levels
260 of DNA fragmentation, are found in 30 to 80% of cases of infertile males⁹⁵. The high content of
261 polyunsaturated fatty acids in germ-cell plasma membranes makes them particularly vulnerable to
262 ROS-mediated damage⁹⁶. Supraphysiological ROS levels also interfere with Sertoli cell function
263 by repressing the expression of integrin beta-1, a key surface molecule for the interaction of Sertoli
264 cells with germ cells, and the expression of connexin-43, a key component of gap junctions⁹⁷.
265 Overall, elevated levels of ROS in COVID-19 patients, which have been implicated in the
266 dysfunction and damage of multiple organs^{68,98}, may also have a negative impact on the
267 reproductive tract.

268 **Cortisol.** Cortisol is a glucocorticoid secreted by the adrenal glands. Its increase under stressful
269 conditions, such as diabetes or inflammation, provides the body with an energy boost for blood
270 glucose control, inflammation reduction, and maintenance of metabolic homeostasis⁹⁹. As
271 expected, a significant increase of serum cortisol concentration is seen in COVID-19 patients¹⁰⁰.
272 However, excessive amounts of cortisol release are linked to detrimental effects on male fertility.
273 For example, elevated serum and salivary cortisol levels correlate with higher incidence of male
274 erectile dysfunction¹⁰¹. Our studies with mice show high levels of cortisol in testicular interstitial
275 fluid and serum of mice with subfertility⁴², further supporting the idea that cortisol can have a
276 negative role in male fertility. We postulate that the combination of inflammation and diabetes in
277 COVID-19 can lead to prolonged excessive levels of cortisol that disrupt optimal hormonal
278 regulation of male fertility; such is found in rats with decreased LH secretion and impaired Leydig
279 cell function^{102,103}.

280 **Triiodothyronine.** This thyroid hormone is a potent regulator of metabolism and development.
281 Low serum levels of triiodothyronine in patients with nonthyroidal illnesses¹⁰⁴ is considered
282 beneficial, as it prevents excessive tissue catabolism¹⁰⁵. COVID-19 patients have reduced
283 concentrations of triiodothyronine (64–84 ng/dL in COVID-19 vs. 82–117 ng/dL in non-COVID-
284 19 patients with 95% confidence interval; $p < 0.01$)¹⁰⁶. From a physiological perspective, this
285 decrease is likely caused by SARS-CoV-2-induced inflammation and/or diabetes, as inflammatory
286 cytokines (IL-1, IL-6, and TNF) are known to inhibit the peripheral conversion of thyroxine to
287 triiodothyronine¹⁰⁷. Moreover, free triiodothyronine is inversely related to the prevalence of both
288 type-1¹⁰⁸ and type-2¹⁰⁹ diabetes in euthyroid patients. Given the broad metabolic functions of
289 triiodothyronine, its decrease can affect multiple organs and/or biological processes. For example,
290 triiodothyronine enhances gonadotropin, LH, and FSH secretion by suppressing mRNA expression
291 of the hypothalamic gonadotropin-inhibitory hormone¹¹⁰. Thus, a decrease in triiodothyronine
292 level can lead to hypogonadism due to insufficient LH and/or FSH levels, as shown by a study
293 with male rats¹¹¹. We speculate that the decline in triiodothyronine level in COVID-19 can
294 contribute to male hypogonadism.

295 **Activins, inhibins, and follistatin.** Activins A and B are members of the transforming growth
296 factor- β superfamily of cytokines. They were initially recognized for their ability to release FSH
297 from the anterior pituitary^{112,113}. Activin A was subsequently found to also stimulate GnRH in the
298 rat hypothalamus¹¹⁴ and in a murine GnRH-secreting neuronal cell line¹¹⁵. Its bioactivity is tightly
299 regulated by two physiological inhibitors: inhibins (A and B) and follistatin, thereby forming the
300 activin/inhibin/follistatin axis¹¹⁶. This metabolic axis is involved in a variety of biological
301 processes, including inflammation and glucose metabolism^{117,118}. Serum levels of activin A,
302 activin B, and follistatin are markedly increased in COVID-19 patients; the levels correlate with

303 disease severity and in-hospital mortality^{119,120}. Since activin A promotes secretion of insulin from
304 cultured pancreatic islet cells¹²¹ and since elevated follistatin expression markedly increases
305 insulin sensitivity in mouse skeletal muscle *in vivo*¹²², it is possible that activation of the
306 activin/inhibin/follistatin axis improves insulin responsiveness and glucose metabolism in
307 COVID-19 patients. However, animal studies indicate that a dysregulated
308 activin/inhibin/follistatin axis can damage the structure and immune environment in the testis and
309 epididymis¹²³. Thus, inflammation and diabetic complications in COVID-19 that disrupt the
310 balance between activins and their antagonists, which is required for maintaining normal male
311 reproductive organ function, can consequently affect male fertility by causing abnormal FSH and
312 LH secretion via the hypothalamic–pituitary–testis axis (HPT) (**Fig. 2**).

313 **Concluding Remarks**

314 We are constantly reminded that COVID-19 is a public health crisis that threatens nearly all aspects
315 of human life, with male patients being more likely than females to suffer from health
316 complications. Given the unprecedented magnitude of the pandemic, its impact on male fertility
317 could be substantial and could have long-lasting geopolitical effects. Inflammation and diabetes
318 are among common co-morbidities of COVID-19. Given their roles as risk factors for male
319 hypogonadism, the interactive detrimental impact of inflammation and diabetes on the
320 reproductive organs of males could be greatly enhanced during COVID-19. Since the infection
321 rate in young adults is increasing¹²⁴, we are concerned that the negative effect on male fertility
322 may occur without severe respiratory symptoms, perhaps several months after acute infection
323 (such has been reported for mumps virus-induced orchitis¹²⁵). With SARS-CoV-2, which likely
324 causes many undetected infections with subclinical organ abnormalities¹²⁶, even a moderate
325 impact on male fertility could have profound population-based effects. To date, clinical studies

326 have not focused on reproductive-age men with mild COVID-19 symptoms; thus, we cannot assess
327 the quantitative importance of virus-mediated sub-fertility. However, the effect of COVID-19
328 complications, in particular inflammation and diabetes, on male fertility should enter prudent
329 considerations of whether to vaccinate.

330

331 **Search strategy and selection criteria**

332 We searched PubMed and Google Scholar for articles published up to September 1, 2021, using
333 the terms “COVID-19”, “SARS-CoV-2”, “COVID-19-associated diabetes”, “COVID-19-
334 associated inflammation”, in combination with “testis”, “male fertility”, “hypothalamic–pituitary–
335 testis axis”, “male reproductive hormones”, “male factors infertility”, “diabetes-associated male
336 infertility”, or “inflammation-associated male infertility”. Articles, and relevant articles in the
337 references of these articles were reviewed. Searches were based on English search terms.

338

339 **Acknowledgements**

340 We thank Ryan Dikdan and Bo Shopsin for critical comments on the manuscript.

341

342 **Conflict of Interest**

343 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

344

345 **Author Contributions**

346 LS, KD, and TL conceived the concept and designed the manuscript outline. QJ, LS, KD, and TL
347 drafted the manuscript and QJ prepared the figures. TL provided clinical insights on diabetes. All
348 authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

349
350
351
352
353
354
355

356 **References**

- 357 1 Guan, W.-J. *et al.* Clinical Characteristics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 in China. *N Engl J Med* **382**,
358 1708-1720, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2002032 (2020).
- 359 2 Zhu, N. *et al.* A Novel Coronavirus from Patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019. *N Engl J Med*
360 **382**, 727-733, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2001017 (2020).
- 361 3 Song, E. *et al.* Neuroinvasion of SARS-CoV-2 in human and mouse brain. *J Exp Med* **218**,
362 doi:10.1084/jem.20202135 (2021).
- 363 4 Puelles, V. G. *et al.* Multiorgan and Renal Tropism of SARS-CoV-2. *N Engl J Med* **383**, 590-592,
364 doi:10.1056/NEJMc2011400 (2020).
- 365 5 Müller, J. A. *et al.* SARS-CoV-2 infects and replicates in cells of the human endocrine and exocrine
366 pancreas. *Nat Metab* **3**, 149-165, doi:10.1038/s42255-021-00347-1 (2021).
- 367 6 Ma, X. *et al.* Pathological and molecular examinations of postmortem testis biopsies reveal SARS-
368 CoV-2 infection in the testis and spermatogenesis damage in COVID-19 patients. *Cell Mol Immunol*
369 **18**, 487-489, doi:10.1038/s41423-020-00604-5 (2021).
- 370 7 Yelin, D. *et al.* Long-term consequences of COVID-19: research needs. *Lancet Infect Dis* **20**, 1115-
371 1117, doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30701-5 (2020).
- 372 8 Holmes, E. *et al.* Incomplete Systemic Recovery and Metabolic Phenoreversion in Post-Acute-
373 Phase Nonhospitalized COVID-19 Patients: Implications for Assessment of Post-Acute COVID-19
374 Syndrome. *Journal of Proteome Research* **20**, 3315-3329, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.1c00224
375 (2021).
- 376 9 Haghpanah, A. *et al.* Potential mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 action on male gonadal function and
377 fertility: Current status and future prospects. *Andrologia* **53**, e13883, doi:10.1111/and.13883
378 (2021).
- 379 10 Safarinejad, M. R. Evaluation of Endocrine Profile, Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Testis Axis and Semen
380 Quality in Multiple Sclerosis. *Journal of Neuroendocrinology* **20**, 1368-1375,
381 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2826.2008.01791.x> (2008).
- 382 11 Abdel-Moneim, A. COVID-19 Pandemic and Male Fertility: Clinical Manifestations and Pathogenic
383 Mechanisms. *Biochemistry (Moscow)* **86**, 389-396, doi:10.1134/s0006297921040015 (2021).
- 384 12 Maresch, C. C. *et al.* Diabetes-induced hyperglycemia impairs male reproductive function: a
385 systematic review. *Hum Reprod Update* **24**, 86-105, doi:10.1093/humupd/dmx033 (2018).
- 386 13 Boddu, S. K., Aurangabadkar, G. & Kuchay, M. S. New onset diabetes, type 1 diabetes and COVID-
387 19. *Diabetes Metab Syndr* **14**, 2211-2217, doi:10.1016/j.dsx.2020.11.012 (2020).

388 14 Stassen, L., Armitage, C. W., van der Heide, D. J., Beagley, K. W. & Frentiu, F. D. Zika Virus in the
389 Male Reproductive Tract. *Viruses* **10**, 198, doi:10.3390/v10040198 (2018).

390 15 Govero, J. *et al.* Zika virus infection damages the testes in mice. *Nature* **540**, 438-442,
391 doi:10.1038/nature20556 (2016).

392 16 Ma, W. *et al.* Zika Virus Causes Testis Damage and Leads to Male Infertility in Mice. *Cell* **167**, 1511-
393 1524.e1510, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2016.11.016> (2016).

394 17 Hviid, A., Rubin, S. & Mühlemann, K. Mumps. *Lancet* **371**, 932-944, doi:10.1016/s0140-
395 6736(08)60419-5 (2008).

396 18 Muciaccia, B. *et al.* HIV-1 viral DNA is present in ejaculated abnormal spermatozoa of seropositive
397 subjects. *Hum Reprod* **22**, 2868-2878, doi:10.1093/humrep/dem288 (2007).

398 19 Shevchuk, M. M., Nuovo, G. J. & Khalife, G. HIV in testis: quantitative histology and HIV localization
399 in germ cells. *J Reprod Immunol* **41**, 69-79, doi:10.1016/s0165-0378(98)00049-7 (1998).

400 20 Poretsky, L., Can, S. & Zumoff, B. Testicular dysfunction in human immunodeficiency virus-
401 infected men. *Metabolism* **44**, 946-953, doi:10.1016/0026-0495(95)90250-3 (1995).

402 21 Pudney, J. & Anderson, D. Orchitis and human immunodeficiency virus type 1 infected cells in
403 reproductive tissues from men with the acquired immune deficiency syndrome. *Am J Pathol* **139**,
404 149-160 (1991).

405 22 De Paepe, M. E. & Waxman, M. Testicular atrophy in AIDS: a study of 57 autopsy cases. *Hum*
406 *Pathol* **20**, 210-214, doi:10.1016/0046-8177(89)90125-1 (1989).

407 23 Hofny, E. R. *et al.* Semen and hormonal parameters in men with chronic hepatitis C infection. *Fertil*
408 *Steril* **95**, 2557-2559, doi:10.1016/j.fertnstert.2011.05.014 (2011).

409 24 Lyu, Z. *et al.* Human papillomavirus in semen and the risk for male infertility: a systematic review
410 and meta-analysis. *BMC Infect Dis* **17**, 714, doi:10.1186/s12879-017-2812-z (2017).

411 25 Hoffmann, M. *et al.* SARS-CoV-2 Cell Entry Depends on ACE2 and TMPRSS2 and Is Blocked by a
412 Clinically Proven Protease Inhibitor. *Cell*, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2020.02.052 (2020).

413 26 Fagerberg, L. *et al.* Analysis of the human tissue-specific expression by genome-wide integration
414 of transcriptomics and antibody-based proteomics. *Mol Cell Proteomics* **13**, 397-406,
415 doi:10.1074/mcp.M113.035600 (2014).

416 27 Wang, Z. & Xu, X. *scRNA-seq Profiling of Human Testes Reveals the Presence of ACE2 Receptor, a*
417 *Target for SARS-CoV-2 Infection, in Spermatogonia, Leydig and Sertoli Cells.* (2020).

418 28 Pushkarsky, T. *et al.* CD147 facilitates HIV-1 infection by interacting with virus-associated
419 cyclophilin A. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*
420 **98**, 6360-6365, doi:10.1073/pnas.111583198 (2001).

421 29 Chen, Z. *et al.* Function of HAb18G/CD147 in invasion of host cells by severe acute respiratory
422 syndrome coronavirus. *J Infect Dis* **191**, 755-760, doi:10.1086/427811 (2005).

423 30 Wang, K. *et al.* CD147-spike protein is a novel route for SARS-CoV-2 infection to host cells. *Signal*
424 *Transduction and Targeted Therapy* **5**, 283, doi:10.1038/s41392-020-00426-x (2020).

425 31 Asgari, R., Mansouri, K., Bakhtiari, M. & Vaisi-Raygani, A. CD147 as an apoptosis regulator in
426 spermatogenesis: deciphering its association with matrix metalloproteinases' pathway. *Mol Biol*
427 *Rep* **46**, 1099-1105, doi:10.1007/s11033-018-4568-y (2019).

428 32 Achua, J. K. *et al.* Histopathology and Ultrastructural Findings of Fatal COVID-19 Infections on
429 Testis. *World J Mens Health* **39**, 65-74 (2021).

430 33 Chen, L. *et al.* Ultrasound Imaging Findings of Acute Testicular Infection in Patients With
431 Coronavirus Disease 2019: A Single-Center-Based Study in Wuhan, China. *J Ultrasound Med*,
432 doi:10.1002/jum.15558 (2020).

433 34 Flaifel, A. *et al.* Testicular Changes Associated With Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
434 Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). *Archives of Pathology & Laboratory Medicine* **145**, 8-9,
435 doi:10.5858/arpa.2020-0487-LE (2020).

436 35 Li, H. *et al.* Impaired spermatogenesis in COVID-19 patients. *EClinicalMedicine* **28**, 100604,
437 doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100604 (2020).

438 36 Ma, L. *et al.* Evaluation of sex-related hormones and semen characteristics in reproductive-aged
439 male COVID-19 patients. *J Med Virol* **93**, 456-462, doi:10.1002/jmv.26259 (2021).

440 37 Salonia, A. *et al.* Severely low testosterone in males with COVID-19: A case-control study.
441 *Andrology*, doi:10.1111/andr.12993 (2021).

442 38 Schuppe, H.-C. *et al.* Chronic orchitis: a neglected cause of male infertility? *Andrologia* **40**, 84-91,
443 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0272.2008.00837.x> (2008).

444 39 Gruschwitz, M. S., Brezinschek, R. & Brezinschek, H. P. Cytokine levels in the seminal plasma of
445 infertile males. *J Androl* **17**, 158-163 (1996).

446 40 Loveland, K. L. *et al.* Cytokines in Male Fertility and Reproductive Pathologies: Immunoregulation
447 and Beyond. *Frontiers in Endocrinology* **8**, doi:10.3389/fendo.2017.00307 (2017).

448 41 Lei, T. *et al.* Galectin-1 enhances TNF α -induced inflammatory responses in Sertoli cells through
449 activation of MAPK signalling. *Scientific Reports* **8**, 3741, doi:10.1038/s41598-018-22135-w
450 (2018).

451 42 Jiang, Q. *et al.* Elevated CCL2 causes Leydig cell malfunction in metabolic syndrome. *JCI Insight* **5**,
452 doi:10.1172/jci.insight.134882 (2020).

453 43 Lainez, N. M. & Coss, D. Leukemia Inhibitory Factor Represses GnRH Gene Expression via cFOS
454 during Inflammation in Male Mice. *Neuroendocrinology* **108**, 291-307, doi:10.1159/000496754
455 (2019).

456 44 Haedo, M. R. *et al.* Regulation of Pituitary Function by Cytokines. *Hormone Research in Paediatrics*
457 **72**, 266-274, doi:10.1159/000245928 (2009).

458 45 Mehta, P. *et al.* COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression. *Lancet*
459 **395**, 1033-1034, doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30628-0 (2020).

460 46 Fijak, M. *et al.* Infectious, inflammatory and 'autoimmune' male factor infertility: how do rodent
461 models inform clinical practice? *Hum Reprod Update* **24**, 416-441, doi:10.1093/humupd/dmy009
462 (2018).

463 47 Yang, M. *et al.* Pathological Findings in the Testes of COVID-19 Patients: Clinical Implications. *Eur*
464 *Urol Focus* **6**, 1124-1129, doi:10.1016/j.euf.2020.05.009 (2020).

465 48 Rastrelli, G. *et al.* Low testosterone levels predict clinical adverse outcomes in SARS-CoV-2
466 pneumonia patients. *Andrology* **9**, 88-98, doi:10.1111/andr.12821 (2021).

467 49 Gacci, M. *et al.* Semen impairment and occurrence of SARS-CoV-2 virus in semen after recovery
468 from COVID-19. *Human Reproduction* **36**, 1520-1529, doi:10.1093/humrep/deab026 (2021).

469 50 Mannur, S., Jabeen, T., Khader, M. A. & Rao, L. S. S. Post-COVID-19-associated decline in long-
470 term male fertility and embryo quality during assisted reproductive technology. *QJM: An*
471 *International Journal of Medicine*, doi:10.1093/qjmed/hcab019 (2021).

472 51 Montefusco, L. *et al.* Acute and long-term disruption of glycometabolic control after SARS-CoV-2
473 infection. *Nature Metabolism* **3**, 774-785, doi:10.1038/s42255-021-00407-6 (2021).

474 52 Chen, S. *et al.* Cytomegalovirus seropositivity is associated with glucose regulation in the oldest
475 old. Results from the Leiden 85-plus Study. *Immun Ageing* **9**, 18, doi:10.1186/1742-4933-9-18
476 (2012).

477 53 Yoon, J. W., Ihm, S. H. & Kim, K. W. Viruses as a triggering factor of type 1 diabetes and genetic
478 markers related to the susceptibility to the virus-associated diabetes. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* **7**
479 **Suppl 1**, S47-58, doi:10.1016/0168-8227(89)90088-0 (1989).

480 54 Roberts, B. W. & Cech, I. Association of type 2 diabetes mellitus and seroprevalence for
481 cytomegalovirus. *South Med J* **98**, 686-692, doi:10.1097/01.Smj.0000163310.12516.2d (2005).

482 55 Ashfaq, U. A. & Khalid, H. Mechanism of Hepatitis C Virus-Induced Diabetes Mellitus. *Crit Rev*
483 *Eukaryot Gene Expr* **27**, 363-371, doi:10.1615/CritRevEukaryotGeneExpr.2017020437 (2017).

484 56 Yang, J. K., Lin, S. S., Ji, X. J. & Guo, L. M. Binding of SARS coronavirus to its receptor damages islets
485 and causes acute diabetes. *Acta Diabetol* **47**, 193-199, doi:10.1007/s00592-009-0109-4 (2010).

486 57 Richardson, S. *et al.* Presenting Characteristics, Comorbidities, and Outcomes Among 5700
487 Patients Hospitalized With COVID-19 in the New York City Area. *JAMA* **323**, 2052-2059,
488 doi:10.1001/jama.2020.6775 (2020).

489 58 Nandy, K. *et al.* Coronavirus disease (COVID-19): A systematic review and meta-analysis to
490 evaluate the impact of various comorbidities on serious events. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome:
491 Clinical Research & Reviews* **14**, 1017-1025, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2020.06.064>
492 (2020).

493 59 Wang, W. *et al.* Elevated glucose level leads to rapid COVID-19 progression and high fatality. *BMC
494 Pulmonary Medicine* **21**, 64, doi:10.1186/s12890-021-01413-w (2021).

495 60 Ren, H. *et al.* Association of the insulin resistance marker TyG index with the severity and mortality
496 of COVID-19. *Cardiovascular Diabetology* **19**, 58, doi:10.1186/s12933-020-01035-2 (2020).

497 61 Codo, A. C. *et al.* Elevated Glucose Levels Favor SARS-CoV-2 Infection and Monocyte Response
498 through a HIF-1 α /Glycolysis-Dependent Axis. *Cell Metab* **32**, 437-446.e435,
499 doi:10.1016/j.cmet.2020.07.007 (2020).

500 62 Zhu, L. *et al.* Association of Blood Glucose Control and Outcomes in Patients with COVID-19 and
501 Pre-existing Type 2 Diabetes. *Cell Metab* **31**, 1068-1077.e1063, doi:10.1016/j.cmet.2020.04.021
502 (2020).

503 63 Mallapaty, S. Mounting clues suggest the coronavirus might trigger diabetes. *Nature* **583**, 16-17,
504 doi:10.1038/d41586-020-01891-8 (2020).

505 64 Rubino, F. *et al.* New-Onset Diabetes in Covid-19. *New England Journal of Medicine* **383**, 789-790,
506 doi:10.1056/NEJMc2018688 (2020).

507 65 Singh, A. K. & Singh, R. Hyperglycemia without diabetes and new-onset diabetes are both
508 associated with poorer outcomes in COVID-19. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* **167**, 108382,
509 doi:10.1016/j.diabres.2020.108382 (2020).

510 66 Liu, F. *et al.* ACE2 Expression in Pancreas May Cause Pancreatic Damage After SARS-CoV-2
511 Infection. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* **18**, 2128-2130.e2122, doi:10.1016/j.cgh.2020.04.040
512 (2020).

513 67 Steenblock, C. *et al.* Viral infiltration of pancreatic islets in patients with COVID-19. *Nature
514 Communications* **12**, 3534, doi:10.1038/s41467-021-23886-3 (2021).

515 68 Laforge, M. *et al.* Tissue damage from neutrophil-induced oxidative stress in COVID-19. *Nat Rev
516 Immunol* **20**, 515-516, doi:10.1038/s41577-020-0407-1 (2020).

517 69 Yuan, M. *et al.* Reversal of Obesity- and Diet-Induced Insulin Resistance with Salicylates or
518 Targeted Disruption of *i>Ikk</i>#x3b2;</i>. *Science* **293**, 1673-1677,
519 doi:doi:10.1126/science.1061620 (2001).*

520 70 Houstis, N., Rosen, E. D. & Lander, E. S. Reactive oxygen species have a causal role in multiple
521 forms of insulin resistance. *Nature* **440**, 944-948, doi:10.1038/nature04634 (2006).

522 71 Gianchandani, R. *et al.* Managing Hyperglycemia in the COVID-19 Inflammatory Storm. *Diabetes
523* **69**, 2048, doi:10.2337/dbi20-0022 (2020).

524 72 Michalakakis, K. & Ilias, I. COVID-19 and hyperglycemia/diabetes. *World J Diabetes* **12**, 642-650,
525 doi:10.4239/wjd.v12.i5.642 (2021).

526 73 Rubino, F. *et al.* New-Onset Diabetes in Covid-19. *N Engl J Med* **383**, 789-790,
527 doi:10.1056/NEJMc2018688 (2020).

528 74 Hasan, M. M. *et al.* Ameliorative effect of combined low dose of Pioglitazone and omega-3 on
529 spermatogenesis and steroidogenesis in diabetic rats. *J Cell Biochem* **121**, 1524-1540,
530 doi:10.1002/jcb.29388 (2020).

531 75 Maresch, C. C. *et al.* Hyperglycemia is associated with reduced testicular function and activin
532 dysregulation in the Ins2(Akita+/-) mouse model of type 1 diabetes. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* **446**, 91-
533 101, doi:10.1016/j.mce.2017.02.020 (2017).

534 76 Khalil, A. S. M. *et al.* Myristic acid defends against testicular oxidative stress, inflammation,
535 apoptosis: Restoration of spermatogenesis, steroidogenesis in diabetic rats. *Life Sci* **278**, 119605,
536 doi:10.1016/j.lfs.2021.119605 (2021).

537 77 Simas, J. N., Mendes, T. B., Fischer, L. W., Vendramini, V. & Miraglia, S. M. Resveratrol improves
538 sperm DNA quality and reproductive capacity in type 1 diabetes. *Andrology* **9**, 384-399,
539 doi:10.1111/andr.12891 (2021).

540 78 Bosman, E., Esterhuizen, A. D., Rodrigues, F. A., Becker, P. J. & Hoffmann, W. A. Effect of
541 metformin therapy and dietary supplements on semen parameters in hyperinsulinaemic males.
542 *Andrologia* **47**, 974-979, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/and.12366> (2015).

543 79 Temidayo, S. & Stefan, S. Diabetes mellitus and male infertility. *Asian Pacific Journal of*
544 *Reproduction* **7**, 6-14, doi:10.4103/2305-0500.220978 (2018).

545 80 Maresch, C. C. *et al.* Hyperglycemia induces spermatogenic disruption via major pathways of
546 diabetes pathogenesis. *Sci Rep* **9**, 13074, doi:10.1038/s41598-019-49600-4 (2019).

547 81 Donath, M. Y. & Shoelson, S. E. Type 2 diabetes as an inflammatory disease. *Nature Reviews*
548 *Immunology* **11**, 98-107, doi:10.1038/nri2925 (2011).

549 82 Esposito, K. *et al.* Inflammatory Cytokine Concentrations Are Acutely Increased by Hyperglycemia
550 in Humans. *Circulation* **106**, 2067-2072, doi:doi:10.1161/01.CIR.0000034509.14906.AE (2002).

551 83 Koenen, T. B. *et al.* Hyperglycemia activates caspase-1 and TXNIP-mediated IL-1beta transcription
552 in human adipose tissue. *Diabetes* **60**, 517-524, doi:10.2337/db10-0266 (2011).

553 84 Dregan, A., Charlton, J., Chowienczyk, P. & Gulliford, M. C. Chronic inflammatory disorders and
554 risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus, coronary heart disease, and stroke: a population-based cohort
555 study. *Circulation* **130**, 837-844, doi:10.1161/circulationaha.114.009990 (2014).

556 85 Aguirre, V., Uchida, T., Yenush, L., Davis, R. & White, M. F. The c-Jun NH(2)-terminal kinase
557 promotes insulin resistance during association with insulin receptor substrate-1 and
558 phosphorylation of Ser(307). *J Biol Chem* **275**, 9047-9054, doi:10.1074/jbc.275.12.9047 (2000).

559 86 Page, S. T., Amory, J. K. & Bremner, W. J. Advances in male contraception. *Endocr Rev* **29**, 465-
560 493, doi:10.1210/er.2007-0041 (2008).

561 87 Eshes, J. A. *et al.* IL-1 antagonism reduces hyperglycemia and tissue inflammation in the type 2
562 diabetic GK rat. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **106**, 13998-14003,
563 doi:10.1073/pnas.0810087106 (2009).

564 88 Kurauti, M. A. *et al.* Interleukin-6 increases the expression and activity of insulin-degrading
565 enzyme. *Scientific Reports* **7**, 46750, doi:10.1038/srep46750 (2017).

566 89 Chen, Y. *et al.* IP-10 and MCP-1 as biomarkers associated with disease severity of COVID-19. *Mol*
567 *Med* **26**, 97, doi:10.1186/s10020-020-00230-x (2020).

568 90 Kleinert, M. *et al.* Animal models of obesity and diabetes mellitus. *Nat Rev Endocrinol* **14**, 140-
569 162, doi:10.1038/nrendo.2017.161 (2018).

570 91 Yang, D. *et al.* Pro-inflammatory cytokines increase reactive oxygen species through mitochondria
571 and NADPH oxidase in cultured RPE cells. *Exp Eye Res* **85**, 462-472,
572 doi:10.1016/j.exer.2007.06.013 (2007).

573 92 Sverrisson, K., Axelsson, J., Rippe, A., Asgeirsson, D. & Rippe, B. Acute reactive oxygen species
574 (ROS)-dependent effects of IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6 on the glomerular filtration barrier (GFB) in vivo.
575 *American Journal of Physiology-Renal Physiology* **309**, F800-F806,
576 doi:10.1152/ajprenal.00111.2015 (2015).

577 93 Volpe, C. M. O., Villar-Delfino, P. H., Dos Anjos, P. M. F. & Nogueira-Machado, J. A. Cellular death,
578 reactive oxygen species (ROS) and diabetic complications. *Cell Death Dis* **9**, 119-119,
579 doi:10.1038/s41419-017-0135-z (2018).

580 94 Petry, S. F., Sharifpanah, F., Sauer, H. & Linn, T. Differential expression of islet glutaredoxin 1 and
581 5 with high reactive oxygen species production in a mouse model of diabetes. *PLoS One* **12**,
582 e0176267, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0176267 (2017).

583 95 Bisht, S., Faiq, M., Tolahunase, M. & Dada, R. Oxidative stress and male infertility. *Nature Reviews*
584 *Urology* **14**, 470-485, doi:10.1038/nrurol.2017.69 (2017).

585 96 Barroso, G., Morshedi, M. & Oehninger, S. Analysis of DNA fragmentation, plasma membrane
586 translocation of phosphatidylserine and oxidative stress in human spermatozoa. *Hum Reprod* **15**,
587 1338-1344, doi:10.1093/humrep/15.6.1338 (2000).

588 97 Zhang, D.-C. *et al.* Hyperactive reactive oxygen species impair function of porcine Sertoli cells via
589 suppression of surface protein ITGB1 and connexin-43. *Zool Res* **41**, 203-207,
590 doi:10.24272/j.issn.2095-8137.2020.024 (2020).

591 98 Chernyak, B. V. *et al.* COVID-19 and Oxidative Stress. *Biochemistry (Mosc)* **85**, 1543-1553,
592 doi:10.1134/S0006297920120068 (2020).

593 99 Thau, L., Gandhi, J. & Sharma, S. in *StatPearls* (StatPearls Publishing
594 Copyright © 2021, StatPearls Publishing LLC., 2021).

595 100 Tan, T. *et al.* Association between high serum total cortisol concentrations and mortality from
596 COVID-19. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol* **8**, 659-660, doi:10.1016/s2213-8587(20)30216-3 (2020).

597 101 Kobori, Y. *et al.* The relationship of serum and salivary cortisol levels to male sexual dysfunction
598 as measured by the International Index of Erectile Function. *Int J Impot Res* **21**, 207-212,
599 doi:10.1038/ijir.2009.14 (2009).

600 102 Ringstrom, S. J. & Schwartz, N. B. Cortisol suppresses the LH, but not the FSH, response to
601 gonadotropin-releasing hormone after orchidectomy. *Endocrinology* **116**, 472-474,
602 doi:10.1210/endo-116-1-472 (1985).

603 103 Gao, H. B. *et al.* Glucocorticoid induces apoptosis in rat leydig cells. *Endocrinology* **143**, 130-138,
604 doi:10.1210/endo.143.1.8604 (2002).

605 104 Maiden, M. J. & Torpy, D. J. Thyroid Hormones in Critical Illness. *Crit Care Clin* **35**, 375-388,
606 doi:10.1016/j.ccc.2018.11.012 (2019).

607 105 Utiger, R. D. Altered thyroid function in nonthyroidal illness and surgery. To treat or not to treat?
608 *N Engl J Med* **333**, 1562-1563, doi:10.1056/nejm199512073332310 (1995).

609 106 Malik, J. *et al.* Thyroid function analysis in COVID-19: A retrospective study from a single center.
610 *PLOS ONE* **16**, e0249421, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0249421 (2021).

611 107 Warner, M. H. & Beckett, G. J. Mechanisms behind the non-thyroidal illness syndrome: an update.
612 *Journal of Endocrinology* **205**, 1-13, doi:10.1677/JOE-09-0412 (2010).

613 108 Perros, P., McCrimmon, R. J., Shaw, G. & Frier, B. M. Frequency of thyroid dysfunction in diabetic
614 patients: value of annual screening. *Diabet Med* **12**, 622-627, doi:10.1111/j.1464-
615 5491.1995.tb00553.x (1995).

616 109 Gu, Y. *et al.* The Relationship Between Thyroid Function and the Prevalence of Type 2 Diabetes
617 Mellitus in Euthyroid Subjects. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism* **102**, 434-442,
618 doi:10.1210/jc.2016-2965 (2016).

619 110 Kiyohara, M., Son, Y. L. & Tsutsui, K. Involvement of gonadotropin-inhibitory hormone in pubertal
620 disorders induced by thyroid status. *Scientific Reports* **7**, 1042, doi:10.1038/s41598-017-01183-8
621 (2017).

622 111 Romano, R. M. *et al.* Triiodothyronine differentially modulates the LH and FSH synthesis and
623 secretion in male rats. *Endocrine* **59**, 191-202, doi:10.1007/s12020-017-1487-y (2018).

624 112 Vale, W. *et al.* Purification and characterization of an FSH releasing protein from porcine ovarian
625 follicular fluid. *Nature* **321**, 776-779, doi:10.1038/321776a0 (1986).

626 113 Ling, N. *et al.* Pituitary FSH is released by a heterodimer of the β -subunits from the two forms of
627 inhibin. *Nature* **321**, 779-782, doi:10.1038/321779a0 (1986).

628 114 Calogero, A. E., Burrello, N., Ossino, A. M., Polosa, P. & D'Agata, R. Activin-A stimulates
629 hypothalamic gonadotropin-releasing hormone release by the explanted male rat hypothalamus:
630 interaction with inhibin and androgens. *J Endocrinol* **156**, 269-274, doi:10.1677/joe.0.1560269
631 (1998).

632 115 González-Manchón, C., Bilezikjian, L. M., Corrigan, A. Z., Mellon, P. L. & Vale, W. Activin-A
633 Modulates Gonadotropin-Releasing Hormone Secretion from a Gonadotropin-Releasing
634 Hormone-Secreting Neuronal Cell Line. *Neuroendocrinology* **54**, 373-377, doi:10.1159/000125916
635 (1991).

636 116 Wijayarathna, R. & de Kretser, D. M. Activins in reproductive biology and beyond. *Human*
637 *Reproduction Update* **22**, 342-357, doi:10.1093/humupd/dmv058 (2016).

638 117 Jones, K. L., de Kretser, D. M., Patella, S. & Phillips, D. J. Activin A and follistatin in systemic
639 inflammation. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* **225**, 119-125, doi:10.1016/j.mce.2004.07.010 (2004).

640 118 Hashimoto, O. & Funaba, M. Activin in glucose metabolism. *Vitam Horm* **85**, 217-234,
641 doi:10.1016/b978-0-12-385961-7.00011-1 (2011).

642 119 Synolaki, E. *et al.* The Activin/Follistatin Axis Is Severely Deregulated in COVID-19 and
643 Independently Associated With In-Hospital Mortality. *J Infect Dis* **223**, 1544-1554,
644 doi:10.1093/infdis/jiab108 (2021).

645 120 McAleavy, M. *et al.* Activin A correlates with the worst outcomes in COVID-19 patients, and can
646 be induced by cytokines via the IKK/NF-kappa B pathway. *bioRxiv*, 2021.2002.2004.429815,
647 doi:10.1101/2021.02.04.429815 (2021).

648 121 Hashimoto, O. & Funaba, M. in *Vitamins & Hormones* Vol. 85 (ed Gerald Litwack) 217-234
649 (Academic Press, 2011).

650 122 Han, X. *et al.* Mechanisms involved in follistatin-induced hypertrophy and increased insulin action
651 in skeletal muscle. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle* **10**, 1241-1257, doi:10.1002/jcsm.12474 (2019).

652 123 Nicolas, N. *et al.* Testicular activin and follistatin levels are elevated during the course of
653 experimental autoimmune epididymo-orchitis in mice. *Scientific reports* **7**, 42391-42391,
654 doi:10.1038/srep42391 (2017).

655 124 Drake, T. M. *et al.* Characterisation of in-hospital complications associated with COVID-19 using
656 the ISARIC WHO Clinical Characterisation Protocol UK: a prospective, multicentre cohort study.
657 *Lancet* **398**, 223-237, doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(21)00799-6 (2021).

658 125 Adamopoulos, D. A., Lawrence, D. M., Vassilopoulos, P., Contoyiannis, P. A. & Swyer, G. I. Pituitary-
659 testicular interrelationships in mumps orchitis and other viral infections. *British medical journal* **1**,
660 1177-1180, doi:10.1136/bmj.1.6121.1177 (1978).

661 126 Oran, D. P. & Topol, E. J. Prevalence of Asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 Infection. *Annals of Internal*
662 *Medicine* **173**, 362-367, doi:10.7326/M20-3012 (2020).

663